

Short communication

***Camponotidea fieberi* Reuter, 1879 (Hemiptera: Miridae),
a genus and species new for the Island of Crete**

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Abstract. The genus *Camponotidea* Reuter, 1879 with *C. fieberi*, Reuter, 1879 (Hemiptera: Miridae) is recorded for the first time from the Island of Crete. Differences between *C. fieberi* and *C. saundersi* (Puton, 1874) are discussed. A new host plant is presented for this Ponto-Mediterranean zoophytophagous species.

Key words: Heteroptera, true bugs, new record, faunistics, distribution, Island of Crete, Greece.

The genus *Camponotidea* Reuter, 1879 takes its name from the similarity of its brachypterous specimens with ants of the genus *Camponotus* Mayr. *Myrmecoris saundersi* Puton, 1874 from Izmir (Turkey), was initially designated as type-species. The revision by Hoberlandt & Jordan (1944) confirmed that it contains two taxa, *Camponotidea fieberi* Reuter, 1879 and *C. saundersi* (Puton, 1874).

The recent checklist of the Heteroptera of the Island Crete (Heckmann *et al.*, 2015) contains 151 taxa of Miridae, but no species of the genus *Camponotidea* was ever collected or photographed.

In this paper, we present the photographic material relating to *C. fieberi*, which is new to the island of Crete and discuss differences between *C. fieberi* and *C. saundersi* with some new bio-ecological data.

Materials examined (Figs 1–2). GREECE: Island of Crete, Chania, prefecture, Sfakia region, Askyfou plateau, altitude 750 meters, 35°17'22.35"N 24°10'57.28"E, 15. VI.2020 1 ex. on *Scolymus hispanicus* (L.) (Asteraceae).

Distribution, European Turkey, Greece. Asia: Turkey, Iran, Iraq, Israel? (Aukema & Rieger, 1999; Linnavuori, 2009; Ghahari & Chérot, 2014). **Genus and species new to the Island of Crete.**

Comparative notes. *Camponotidea fieberi* (Figs 1–2) is very similar to the Mediterranean *C. saundersi* (Puton, 1874) (Figs 3–4), but both can be separated according to the following characters: ***Camponotidea fieberi*** (Fig. 5). Labium reaching anterior coxae, third antennal segment 0.5 times the second, apex of hemelytra, in brachypterous specimens, with a wider cres-

cent-shaped pale area; ***C. saundersi*** (Fig. 6) Labium reaching median coxae, third antennal article 0.6-0.7 times the second, apex of hemelytra, in brachypterous specimens, with a thin pale horizontal line away from the posterior border.

Figs 1–4. 1–2. *Camponotidea fieberi* from Crete 1. on a flower of *Scolymus hispanicus* (photo F. Samaritakis), 2. sucking the stem of *Scolymus hispanicus*. 3–4. *Camponotidea saundersi* from Apulia. 3. on *Teucrium capitatum* L. ssp. *capitatum* (L.) (photo G. C. Pasquali), 4. on *Onobrychis caput-galli* (L.) Lam (photo G. C. Pasquali).

Figs 5–6. The apical white/yellow spots on the hemelytra. 5. *Camponotidea fieberi* (Turkey), 6. *C. saundersi* (Italy) (photos P. Dioli).

Remarks on biology

Camponotidea fieberi is a zoophytophagous species, but its detailed biology is little known. Its behaviour as a predator seems to be generalistic since, in Ukraine, its myrmecophagy was recently documented (Çerçi, 2019), and in Crete, *Scolymus hispanicus* (L.) (Asteraceae) was in the present paper recorded as its new host plant (Figs 1–2). Seidenstücker (1959) reported it as numerous on *Salvia horminum* (L.) (Lamiaceae) in Turkey, in the cultural area on paths, railway embankments, and meadow edges; several specimens were also caught on *Vicia* sp. often streaked with herbaceous vegetation, but never together with ants.

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